

Assessment of biological potency of commercially available vancomycin products in Jordan using USP cylinder–plate assay

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Abstract

Background: Recent reports raising concerns regarding the clinical performance of vancomycin products in Jordan prompted a regulatory review focused on biological potency.

Objective: To evaluate the biological potency of commercially available vancomycin products using the United States Pharmacopeia (USP) cylinder–plate assay method.

Methods: Four different vancomycin hydrochloride products (designated as Product A, Product B, Product C, and Product D) from various batches were assessed using the USP cylinder–plate assay, with *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6633 as the indicator organism. Potency calculations were performed using standard curve analysis and expressed as a percentage of labeled potency.

Results: Significant variability in biological potency was observed across the tested products. Several batches of Product A and comparative products failed to meet the USP acceptance criteria of 90–115% potency. A potential correlation between batch age and potency was observed, suggesting a possible association between increased batch age and lower potency. More recent batches in this sample set met the USP acceptance range, whereas at least one older batch showed reduced potency (78.3%); however, storage and thermal history were not documented, so causality cannot be inferred.

Conclusion: The study identified potency-related concerns for some vancomycin products in Jordan. The findings suggest that enhanced post-market surveillance and adherence to proper storage protocols are important to help ensure that products meet potency specifications.

Keywords

cylinder–plate assay, Jordan, pharmaceutical quality control, potency testing, vancomycin

Introduction

Vancomycin hydrochloride is a lipopeptide antibiotic that serves as a critical therapeutic agent against serious Gram-positive bacterial infections, particularly

methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) (Cheng et al. 2022). Since its clinical introduction in 1958, vancomycin has maintained its position as a drug of last resort for life-threatening infections resistant to other

antibiotics (Zuluaga et al. 2015). The therapeutic efficacy of vancomycin is directly dependent on maintaining adequate biological potency, defined as the biological activity of the antibiotic preparation.

The assessment of antibiotic potency requires specialized analytical methods that can accurately measure biological activity rather than merely chemical composition. Chemical analytical methods, while precise for quantifying active pharmaceutical ingredients, may not detect reductions in biological activity caused by degradation products or structural modifications that compromise antimicrobial efficacy (Dafale et al. 2016). Consequently, microbiological assays remain the gold standard for potency determination of antibiotics, as mandated by regulatory authorities worldwide.

The United States Pharmacopeia (USP) provides standardized protocols for antibiotic potency testing through the cylinder–plate assay (CPA), detailed in General Chapter <81> (United States Pharmacopeia 2024). This method relies on the diffusion of the antibiotic through an agar medium and subsequent measurement of growth inhibition zones around standardized cylinders containing the test solutions. The biological activity is determined by comparing the inhibition zones produced by test samples against those produced by reference standards of known potency.

In Jordan, healthcare providers recently reported concerns regarding the clinical effectiveness of certain vancomycin preparations, prompting the Jordanian Food and Drug Administration (JFDA) to initiate quality investigations. These reports suggested potential reductions in therapeutic efficacy, raising questions about the biological potency and stability of commercially available products. The University of Petra Pharmaceutical Center (UPPC), as the only laboratory in Jordan certified for vancomycin potency testing according to USP protocols, was commissioned to conduct this investigation.

This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of the biological potency of multiple vancomycin products available in the Jordanian market, employing the USP cylinder–plate assay to assess their potency and compliance with established quality standards. The findings have significant implications for pharmaceutical regulation, clinical practice, and public health in Jordan and similar markets, underscoring the need for robust post-market surveillance programs.

Materials and methods

Test materials and sample collection

A total of 40 vancomycin hydrochloride vials (500 mg each), presented as imported, lyophilized powder for injection, were collected from four different manufacturers commercially available in Jordan. The products were anonymized and designated as Product A, Product B, Product C, and Product D. Product A included samples from four different batches obtained from various healthcare facilities, while Product B, Product C, and Product D were represented by

two batches each from local market sources. All samples were stored at 2–8 °C until analysis and were within their labeled expiry dates at the time of testing (Table 1).

Table 1. Vancomycin products tested in the study.

Product code	Number of batches	Number of vials	Expiry date range
A	4	16	25 Feb to 26 Nov
B	2	8	26 Oct
C	2	8	27 Dec
D	2	8	26 Oct

Microorganisms and culture media

The standard test organism *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 6633 was obtained from Microbiologics Inc. (USA) and maintained according to USP specifications. Stock cultures were preserved in 10–15% glycerol in tryptic soy broth (Oxoid, UK) at –80 °C for long-term storage. Working cultures were maintained on nutrient agar slants at 4 °C and subcultured every 2–5 days to ensure viability and consistent performance.

For assay preparation, Medium 8 (Himedia, USA) was used for inoculum preparation, while Medium 32 (Himedia, USA) served as the base layer for the cylinder–plate assay. The composition and preparation of these media followed USP specifications exactly as described in General Chapter <81>.

Reference standards and solution preparation

USP Reference Standard vancomycin hydrochloride (Lot: 1709007) was used. A primary stock solution (1000 µg/mL) was prepared in sterile distilled water. From this, three working standard solutions were prepared daily using Buffer 4 (phosphate buffer, pH 6.0, Himedia, USA) as the diluent: 5.0 µg/mL (S1), 10.0 µg/mL (S2), and 15.0 µg/mL (S3).

Test sample preparation

Samples were prepared by reconstituting vancomycin vials with 10.0 mL of sterile distilled water. For each batch, a single pooled stock solution was created by mixing the contents of three randomly selected vials. Aliquots from this master pool were then used for each of the five independent assay runs, with fresh dilutions prepared for each run. From each pooled solution, appropriate dilutions were prepared using Buffer 4 to achieve a theoretical concentration of 10.0 µg/mL.

Cylinder–plate assay procedure

The assay was performed according to USP General Chapter <81>. A fresh culture of *B. subtilis* was used to prepare an inoculum suspension equivalent to a 0.5 McFarland standard. This suspension was spread uniformly over Medium 32 agar plates. Six stainless steel cylinders were

placed on each inoculated plate. Each cylinder was filled with 200 μL of a standard or test solution. Plates were incubated at 32–35 °C for 16–18 hours.

Experimental design and replication

The potency of each batch was determined across five independent assay runs conducted on different days. In each run, three replicate plates were used. The 15 replicates reported for each standard concentration and test batch are the result of measurements from these five runs \times three plates.

Zone measurement and data collection

After incubation, the diameters of clear zones of growth inhibition were measured to the nearest 0.1 mm using a calibrated digital caliper (Marketlab, USA). Each zone was measured in two perpendicular directions, and the average was recorded. Measurements were performed by the same analyst under consistent lighting conditions.

Potency calculations and statistical analysis

Potency calculations followed the procedures in USP General Chapter <81>. A correction factor was applied to account for plate-to-plate variation. A linear regression of corrected zone diameters versus the logarithm of standard concentrations was constructed. The potency of each test sample was calculated from the regression equation and expressed as a percentage of the labeled amount.

Statistical validation

The assay was considered valid based on predefined acceptance criteria. The coefficient of determination (R^2) for the standard curve was required to be ≥ 0.98 . The relative standard deviation (RSD) for replicate zone measurements was required to be $\leq 10\%$. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to confirm the parallelism of the dose–response curves for the test samples and the reference standard.

Results

Assay validation parameters

The cylinder–plate assay demonstrated strong analytical performance. The precision of the method was confirmed by low RSD values for zone diameter measurements (S1: 4.94%, S2: 5.50%, S3: 4.56%), all below the 10% acceptance criterion.

The linearity of the standard curve was established across five independent assay runs, as shown in Table 2. An ANOVA of the regression lines confirmed no significant deviation from parallelism between the standard and test sample response curves ($F(2, 8) = 1.84, p > 0.05$), validating the potency calculations.

Table 2. Run-level regression outputs for the standard curve.

Assay Run	Slope (b)	Intercept (a)	R^2
1	3.18	11.05	0.9981
2	3.25	10.98	0.9954
3	3.09	11.12	0.9816
4	3.21	11.01	0.9972
5	3.15	11.08	0.9965

Potency assessment results

The calculated potency values revealed significant variability. Based on the USP acceptance criteria of 90.0–115.0% potency, Batch 4 of Product A and Batch 1 of Product B failed to meet the required standards. The potency results are summarized in Table 3 and Figs 1, 2.

Table 3. Calculated potency of vancomycin product batches.

Product	Batch	Calculated potency (%)	Standard deviation (SD)
Product A	1	95.2	3.1
	2	101.8	4.5
	3	97.4	3.8
	4	78.3	5.2
Product B	1	89.2	4.9
	2	94.5	3.5
Product C	1	103.7	4.1
	2	101.1	3.9
Product D	1	91.8	4.6
	2	93.2	4.2

Discussion

This investigation provides evidence of biological potency variability among commercially available vancomycin products in Jordan. The findings demonstrate that while most tested batches meet established quality standards, exceptions exist that raise concerns about product consistency.

The observed potency failures align with established knowledge of vancomycin stability. Vancomycin is susceptible to degradation, a process accelerated by elevated temperatures and extended storage periods (Nambiar et al. 2012). The potential correlation between batch age and potency reduction observed in this study suggests that storage conditions and supply chain management may play important roles in maintaining drug quality. However, as the thermal history of the batches was not documented, this remains a hypothesis. Studies by Masse et al. (2020) have shown that vancomycin stability is highly dependent on storage temperature.

Our findings differ from some investigations in other markets. A study by Hadwiger et al. (2012) found that all tested vancomycin products in the US met USP specifications, highlighting potential differences in manufacturing, regulation, and supply chain management. This disparity underscores the importance of robust local quality control and post-market surveillance programs (Zuluaga et al. 2009; de la Fuente-Nunez et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Corrected mean zone of inhibition for vancomycin standards and test products. The bar chart displays the corrected mean diameters of growth inhibition zones. The error bars represent the standard deviation (SD), which was calculated from the set of 15 individual zone diameter measurements ($n = 15$) obtained from five independent assay runs (three replicate plates per run) for each respective sample. USP reference standards show consistent performance, while Product A batches demonstrate variable potency, with Batch 4 showing significantly reduced inhibition zones indicative of sub-potent activity.

Figure 2. Calculated biological potency of vancomycin products. Potency values are expressed as a percentage of the labeled amount (500 mg/vial) for all tested products. The green shaded area represents the USP acceptable range (90–115%). Products falling below this range are considered sub-potent.

The use of the microbiological assay was essential for detecting biologically relevant potency reductions that might not be apparent through chemical analysis alone (Zuluaga et al. 2015; Deneke et al. 2024). The implications of sub-potent antibiotic preparations are a significant public health concern (Capuzzo et al. 2024). Inadequate antibiotic exposure may increase the risk of suboptimal clinical response and may contribute to antimicrobial re-

sistance, underscoring the importance of maintaining potency within specification (Claudius et al. 1998; Deneke et al. 2024; Mashuri et al. 2025). The identification of sub-potent vancomycin products in this study highlights the importance of regulatory surveillance.

This study has several limitations. The sample size for comparative products was limited. The study did not include chemical analysis to identify specific degradation

products. Furthermore, the vial pooling strategy means that the reported potency reflects the average of the tested vials for each run, and no statistical inference can be made about the potency of individual, untested vials within a batch. Future investigations could incorporate both microbiological and chemical methods to provide a more complete understanding of quality issues.

Despite these limitations, the study provides compelling evidence for the need for enhanced pharmaceutical quality control in Jordan. The findings support recommendations for improved storage and handling protocols and more frequent quality testing of antibiotic products.

Conclusion

This study employed the USP cylinder–plate assay to evaluate the biological potency of commercially available vancomycin products in Jordan. The results demonstrate variability in potency among different products and batches, with some failing to meet USP standards. The observed potential correlation between batch age and potency reduction highlights the importance of proper storage and supply chain management.

The findings suggest a need for enhanced post-market surveillance of antibiotic products to ensure compliance with quality standards. These findings support enhanced post-market surveillance and reinforce the importance of appropriate storage and supply-chain controls to help ensure products remain within potency specifications.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

We have used Manus AI in providing better quality of the figures and in plagiarism check of what we have wrote in this manuscript so to avoid plagiarism of more than 12%

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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